

Turning Negative Rural Storylines into Attractive Rural Places in Honey Business

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(Photo: Sugar Daddies Honey Company)
Sugar Daddies entrepreneurs carrying a beehive in forest

Turning negative rural storylines into narratives of attractive rural places is a marketing and branding method in which emphasising authentic connection to place by turning negative rural features to positive imaginaries is used. *Sugar Daddies Honey Company* in Western Finland is one example of enterprises in which turning negative rural storylines into attractive rural places can be identified in branding and marketing. The company sells more than just honey - it sells even more so rural imaginaries that appeal to its customers, especially in urban environments.

Sugar Daddies Honey Company was established by a small circle of friends who enjoyed surfing together and started to wonder if chemical-free ecological surfing wax options existed. Their first idea was to create an ecological surfing wax to suit cold water surfing. Consequently, they invested in a few beehives to soon realise that honey will be their main product. Now, the honey is sold under a few different brand names. It is collected from the fields and forests of the Finnish village of Isokyrö. *Sugar Daddies Honey Company* is active in social media where for instance photos of old machinery, old buildings and reality of honey production work done in field is posted. Starting from the name of the company, *Sugar Daddies Honey Company*, marketing is playing with different imaginaries that their customers may attach to words used.

The concept of turning negative rural storylines into narratives of attractive rural places (sexing up or glamorising rural places) consists of mixing story, history and locality with generational experience, rural and urban mix, and visual and aesthetic emphasis on clarity and minimalism in marketing and branding through giving emphasis to negative features associated with countryside. As agroforestry products are typically produced in the countryside, in story telling through turning negative rural storylines into attractive rural places, farmers sell more than a product – they sell imaginaries, emotional connections to a place and feelings of belonging to rural place.

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Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.